

"PROBLEMS OF FAMILY AND MARRIAGE IN THE LIFE AND WORK OF A.PUSHKIN"

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Abstract: The article discusses the theme of family in the life and work of A.S. Pushkin on the example of the analysis of his poems and the novel in verse "Eugene Onegin"

Keywords:.... The theme of the family, moral problems, the lyrics of A.S.Pushkin, the novel in verse "Eugene Onegin", themes and motives of creativity, universal values

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The theme of family is one of the most significant in Russian literature. Different writers have their own unique, creative approach to this problem, but the motive and the problems remain common. According to this, thanks to the family, moral foundations and universal values are established, which eventually pass from generation to generation.

It so happened that in the life of Alexander Sergeevich, his parents did not play a significant role. Meanwhile, the poet warmly treated his brothers and sisters.

She and Olga were especially close emotionally and spiritually. The poet's attitude towards his sister was very friendly, starting from childhood until the very last hour. Her moods and interests were clear and close to him. She was a companion of his childhood games, treated her brother with special care and love. Olga grew up a well-read girl. She preferred to talk with books, putting this occupation above all.

There is a poem that was dedicated to Olga, his sister:

Do you want, priceless friend,
So that I am a younger poet,
Talked to you
And with a forgotten lyre,
Inspired by dreams,
Left the monastery
And the edge is secluded.

The poet's nanny is Arina Rodionovna, it was she who created for him in childhood an atmosphere of love and comfort that even his parents could not give him. Pushkin was very sensitive to his nanny and always spoke of her with great

warmth. The poet used her image to create several of his literary heroines, several times dedicated the poems "Winter Evening", "Nanny", "I am not happy with my talkativeness" to the nurse.

A friend of my harsh days,
My decrepit dove!
Alone in the wilderness of pine forests
For a long, long time you've been waiting for me.

This poem is a message that is permeated with warmth, respect and gratitude. It was created in the form of a monologue-an appeal to her. Every line of it is a detail of a portrait of an elderly woman close to her soul.

The family of Alexander Sergeevich Pushkin himself was ideal for him. Natalia Goncharova, his wife, They were happily married. This is evidenced by his numerous surviving letters to his wife and friends. "I am married and happy," he wrote to his friend Pyotr Pletnev. A.S. Pushkin dedicated many of his poems to his wife. One of them is "Madonna":

My wishes have been fulfilled. The Creator
Sent you to me, you, my Madonna,
The purest charm is the purest sample.

This poem is a monologue of the lyrical hero, which gradually reveals the author's idea of an ideal family, an ideal woman.

The concept of family in the works of A.S. Pushkin is also revealed in his best work - the novel in verse "Eugene Onegin". In the works of Yu. M. Lotman dedicated to A.S. Pushkin, the importance of the words "home" and "family" for the writer was noted [3, 75].

And in the novel "Eugene Onegin", the Larin family occupies a central place. The surname of the Larins was chosen for a reason, there is a subtext in it - the Larins were the household deities of the ancient Romans, the patrons of the hearth.

Dmitry Larin is the head of the family, he loved his wife cordially, "he believed in everything carelessly", he entrusted her with the management of the household and expenses.

Praskovya Larina, according to the author's description, is a typical lady-serf. In her youth, she was characterized by sentimentality. She was fond of novels, was in love with a "nice dandy", but after getting married, she moved to the village and became an ordinary landowner.

Mrs. Larina loved her daughters in her own way, and like any mother wanted to see them happy, dreamed of successfully marrying them off.

The image of the daughter - Olga Larina is an absolute copy of her mother. Later, in his works devoted to the work of A.S. Pushkin, V.G. Belinsky will note that she "from a graceful and sweet girl will become a remarkable lady, repeating her mother, with small changes that time required."

This is followed by a conclusion - by creating the image of Olga, Pushkin wanted to show the problem of that time, when an outwardly attractive shell is by no means evidence of a rich inner world of a person. According to the author, Olga is a classic example of a noblewoman of that era. She should continue her family and live her life, taking an example from her mother. However, thanks to the image of Olga, Pushkin manages to use the antithesis to very successfully describe the inner beauty, spiritual depth and purity of her sister Tatiana.

"Pushkin does not escalate the topic of confrontation between two sisters, does not create a conflict of enmity or rivalry between them. But the interaction of the images and destinies of Tatiana and Olga plays an important role in the figurative system and ideological structure of the novel, not being reduced to the external contrast brought to the fore and deliberately played out" [4, 127].

Tatiana's alienness in her family does not affect her relationship with her sister Olga in any way. They are very attached to each other. Nevertheless, Tatiana enjoys respect in the family circle. A vivid example of this is Tatiana's magnificent name day.

For researchers of Tatiana's image, her marriage is nothing but a "failure" in the general logic of her character. According to V.A. Koshelev, "The finale of "poor Tanya" is very unexpected for the reader when she decided to become the wife of an unloved "fat general", refusing other suitors. She justifies her action with the words: "My mother begged me with tears of spells..." [2. 157-158]. According to Belinsky, the novel is "an encyclopedia of Russian life at the beginning of the XIX century. The novel "Eugene Onegin - a realistic work" [1, 98]. Maybe A. Pushkin - the author, precisely following the truth of life, led his main character exactly along this line of fate.

So, the theme of the family in the works of A.S. Pushkin is revealed in many ways:

1. the role of sincere and pure relationships between people,
2. the theme of love and marital duty,
3. moral purity and external beauty,
4. the theme of the family as the basis of moral relations in society.

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